

Comparative Toxicity Studies of Fruit and Leaves Extract of *Ziziphus Mauritiana* Plant

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Abstract

The preliminary phytochemical screening and Toxicological studies of fruit and leaves extract of *Ziziphus mauritiana* was carried out. High percentage yield was obtain from aqueous extract followed by leaves ethanolic and fruit ethylacetate extracts. The result indicate the presence of all major phytoconstituents. Anthraquinone was not found in leave extract as well as in the aqueous and ethanolic extract of the fruit. The brine shrimp lethality assay revealed that aqueous fruit extract was not toxic but the extract from leaves, ethanol and ethylacetate were found to be toxic. Therefore, the result of this work clearly revealed that the ethanol and ethylacetate extract from this plant is a potential toxin when taken in traditional medicine.

Keywords: BSLA, Extracts, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, Toxicity

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Introduction

Ziziphus mauritiana specie is a family of Rhamnaceae have been in use in folklore medicine over a long period for various ailments and various phytochemicals (secondary metabolites) have been generally implicated in adverse bioactivities (Owolarafe *et al.*, 2020). The plant is also Known as Indian jujube, Chineses date and magarya in Hausa language Northern Nigeria. It is an evergreen shrub mostly found in temperate region of the world (Morton, 1987, Kaleem *et al.*, 2014, Dahiru *et al.*, 2005). Various solvent extract of *Ziziphus mauritiana* extracts different extract reveals the presence of secondary metabolites, this may be due to difference in polarity of the extracting media. The ethanolic leave extract reveals the presence of Alkaloids, cardiac glycoside, polyphenols, resin, and tannin, carbohydrate, protein (Bitwell *et. al.*, 2023; Abalaka *et al.*, 2011, Senthil Rajan *et al.*, 2013), the aqueous extract shows the presence of Alkaloids, cardiac glycoside, polyphenols, resin, saponin and tannin, carbohydrate, protein and phytosterols (Javed *et. al.*, 2022; Abalaka *et al.*, 2011, Senthil Rajan *et al.*, 2013).

The extracts of the fruit exhibits high phenolic compounds with the preliminary phytochemical studies of the fruit methanol extract revealing the presence of flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, steroids, terpenoids and tannins (Najafi, 2013; Okala *et al.*, 2014). The phenolic compounds in the fruit are phenolic acids such as gallic acid, vanillic acid, m-coumaric acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, p- coumaric, and o- coumaric, Also flavonoids such as myricitin, ratin, morin, diosmin, quercetin, naringenin, kaempferol, chrysin and 5-hydrox flavone were also detected (Naseer *et al.*, 2018; Memon *et al.*, 2012). The aim of this study is to evaluate the

toxicological effect of different solvent extracts of *Z. mauritiana* plant using brine shrimp lethality assay model.

Materials and Methods

Plant material and Authentication

The fruit and leaves of *Z. mauritiana* plant used in this study were obtained from the premises of Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria and authenticated at the herbarium unit of the department of Plant Biology, Bayero University Kano with a voucher Number BUKHAN 0233 and the plant specimen was deposited.

Extract Preparation

The preparation of extract was carried-out according to the method of Owolarafe *et al.* (2020). Briefly, fresh leaves and the mesocarp of the fruit were dried in the shade for two (2) weeks, pulverized into powder and stored in air tight plastic container. The pulverized leaves of *Z. mauritiana* were weighed and 500 g of the powdered material were macerated and extracted in 2000 cm³ of Aqueous, ethanol and ethylacetate for 72 h. The extracted samples were sieved and filtered using sieve cloth and Whatman filter paper (Number 1). The filtrate was concentrated with rotary evaporator and used for the study.

Phytochemical Screening

The phytochemical composition of the leaves and fruit of extracts were determine using standard protocols (Sofowora, 1993; Edeoga *et al.*,2005).

Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BSLA)

The protocol of Miller and Tainter was adopted as described by Randhawa, 2009 and Lilybeth and Olga 2013. Brine shrimp eggs were obtained from the ocean Nutrition, Belgium for this research work. Filtered, seawater was obtained from the bar beach Lagos state Nigeria for hatching the shrimp eggs. The seawater was put in a small plastic container (hatching chamber) with a partition for dark (covered) and light areas. Shrimp eggs were added into the dark side of the chamber while the lamp above the other side (light) will attract the hatched shrimp. Two days were allowed for the shrimp to hatch and mature as nauplii (larva). After two days, when the shrimp larvae are ready, 4 mL of the seawater was added to each test tube and 10 brine shrimps were introduced into each tube. Each concentration were prepared in triplicate Thus, there were a total of 30 shrimps per dilution. Then the volume was adjusted with seawater up to 5 mL per test tube. The test tubes were left uncovered under the lamp. The number of surviving shrimps were counted and recorded after 24 hours. Using probit analysis, the lethality concentration (LC50) was assessed at 95% confidence intervals. LC50 value of less than 1000 µg/mL is toxic while LC50 value of greater than 1000 µg/mL is non-toxic. The percentage mortality (%M) was also calculated by dividing the number of dead nauplii by the total number, and then multiplied by 100%. This is to ensure that the death (mortality) of the nauplii is attributed to the bioactive compounds present in the plant extracts and the potency of the extracts.

Results

The percentage yield of various extracts using different solvents are presented in table 1, which revealed that, the percentage yield for leaves extracts range from 1.47 to 8.5 % for ethanolic and aqueous extract while for fruit extract, highest yield was recorded for aqueous extract (12.29%).

Table 1: Percentage yield of *Ziziphus mauritiana* leaves and Fruit mesocarp

SOLVENT/SAMPLE TYPE	LEAVES	FRUIT (MESOCARP)
AQUEOUS	8.50 %	12.29 %
ETHANOL	1.47 %	8.05 %
ETHYLACETATE	2.50 %	1.53 %

Phytochemical screening of extracts of leaf and fruit mesocarp revealed the presence alkaloids, phenols, tannin and steroid while both plant parts showed absence of anthraquinone. The ethylacetate leaf extract showed absence of Saponin, glycoside while the fruit mesocarp showed absence of flavonoids. Triterpenes are absent in aqueous and ethanol extracts while flavonoids is absent in ethylacetate extract of *Z. mauritiana* fruit mesocarp

Table 2: Phytochemical Screening Of *Ziziphus mauritiana* Leaf Extracts

S/N	PHYTOCHEMICALS	Aqueous	Ethanol	Ethylacetate
1	Alkaloids	√	√	√
2	Saponin	√	√	*
3	Glycosides	√	√	*
4	Triterpenes	√	√	√
5	Phenol	√	√	√
6	Tannin	√	√	√
7	Flavonoid	√	√	√
8	Steroid	√	√	√
9	Anthraquinone	*	*	*

KEY: √ = Present * = Absent

Table 3: Phytochemical Screening of *Ziziphus mauritiana* Fruit mesocarp Extracts

	PHYTOCHEMICALS	Aqueous	Ethanol	Ethylacetate
1	Alkaloids	√	√	√
2	Saponin	√	√	√
3	Glycosides	√	√	√
4	Triterpenes	*	*	√
5	Phenol	√	√	√
6	Tannin	√	√	√
7	Flavonoid	√	√	*
8	Steroid	√	√	√
9	Anthraquinone	*	*	*

KEY: √ = Present * = Absent

The brine shrimp lethality bioassay result of *Ziziphus mauritiana* leaves and fruit mesocarp are presented in Table 4 and 5. The lethal concentrations (LC₅₀) of leaf extracts were lower than that

of fruit mesocarp extracts also ethanol extract of both plant parts revealed the lowest LC₅₀ (64.37 and 93.33 µg/ml). The aqueous extract of the leaf presented the highest LC₅₀ and are classified non-toxic. All ethanol and ethylacetate extracts of both plant parts are toxic or moderately toxic based on Clarkson and Meyer toxicity index classification.

Table 4: Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay of leaves extracts of *Z. Mauritiana*

Extract	Dose (µg/ml)	Percentage Mortality	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	Toxicity Classification
aqueous (Leaves extract)	0	0	536001.788	Non toxic
	10	0		
	100	0		
	1000	0		
Ethanol (leaves extract)	0	0	64.37	Toxic/Moderately toxic
	10	60		
	100	100		
	1000	100		
Ethylacetate (Leaves extract)	0	0	103.51	Toxic /Moderately toxic
	10	50		
	100	100		
	1000	100		

Note: Toxicity classification is according, to the Meyer's and Clarkson's toxicity index

Table 5: Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay of Fruit Mesocarp extracts of *Z. mauritiana*

Extract	Dose (µg/ml)	Percentage Mortality	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	Toxicity Classification
Aqueous (fruit Mesocarp extract)	0	0	279.88	Slightly toxic/ Non Toxic
	10	20		
	100	40		
	1000	60		
Ethanol (fruit Mesocarp extract)	0	0	93.33	Toxic /moderately toxic
	10	30		
	100	100		
	1000	100		
Ethylacetate (fruit Mesocarp extract)	0	0	109.65	Toxic /moderately toxic
	10	60		
	100	100		
	1000	100		

Note: Toxicity classification is according, to the Meyer's and Clarkson's toxicity index

DISCUSSION

The extraction of plant phytoconstituents is influenced by various factors ranging from type of solvent used, their polarity, plant part to be used and the nature of the plant in terms of cell membrane composition (Arslanyolu and Erdemgil, 2006; Farhat et al., 2020; Pimentel Montanher *et al.*, 2002). The prepared extracts differ in quantities and bioactive components (phytochemicals). The results from this study showed aqueous solvent yielded the highest percentage, this may be due to high polarity of the solvent and its ability to rupture the plant cell membrane thereby releasing a larger plant constituent due to the nature of the plant cell membrane chemical composition (Bitwell *et al.*, 2023; Arslanyolu and Erdemgil, 2006). Phytochemical constituents of extracts are fundamental to their bioactivity of such extract. Solvents of various types are used for extraction of plant bioactive components and the resulting extracts usually contain different phytoconstituents, this may be due to the nature of the plant material, extraction process and extracting potential of the solvent used (Ahmed et al., 2010; Ogugu et al., 2012; Veni and Pushpanathan, 2014; Mentor *et al.*, 2014). This is evident in the phytochemicals observed in the extracts of leaf and fruit mesocarp of *Z. mauritiana* plant. This is corroborated by the work of El-Mannoubi (2023), Savic and Savic Gajic (2023) and Vieito et al., (2018).

The need for alternative to the use of animal model in toxicological tests is very important (Balls, 2022; Pallocca *et al.*, 2022) and *Artemia salina* bioassay for predicting the toxicity of plant extracts have been reported as a very good alternative (Ho *et al.*, 2022). Also, the correlation or comparison of these two models have been reported (Azra *et al.*, 2022; Sharma *et al.*, 2013; Naidu *et al.*, 2014; Parra *et al.*, 2001; Syahmi *et al.*, 2010) using the LC_{50} values of BSLA and LD_{50} value using Swiss albino mice.

Various extracts of *Z. mauritiana* plant parts used are biologically active with highest toxicity exhibited by ethanol extract of the fruit mesocarp and leaf while the lowest activity was observed in their aqueous extract. Therefore, administration of these extracts in traditional medicine practice maybe carried-out with profound caution, this corroborate the submission of Balarastaghi *et al.*, 2022). This is in-line with the study of Sahgal et al., (2010).

Conclusion

The result from this research suggests that extracts from this plant are moderately toxic and their administration may lead to profound adverse effect especially in long term administration.

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